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Effect of Gagne Learning Strategy on Motivation in Computer Networking among Secondary School Students in Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of Gagne learning Strategy on Motivation in Computer Networking among Secondary School Students in Gusau, Zamfara State. The study was guided by two objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses were also formulated. Mixed research design (quasi experimental and survey designs) was employed. The sample size of 98 students was selected using purposive sampling technique. Two instruments namely Computer Networking Performance Test (CNPT) and the computer networking motivation questionnaire (CNMQ) were used in the process of data collection. Descriptive statistics was used to answer the research questions and inferential statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings indicated that the performance of students taught Computer Networking concept using Gagne's nine levels of learning strategy was significantly better than those taught with discussion method. It was recommended that Gagne's nine levels of learning strategy should be employed in other topics of data processing and in other science subjects by teachers.

Keyword: Gagne learning strategy, motivation, computer Networking

Introduction

Gagne's model of learning strategy is based on the information processing model of the mental events that occur when learners are presented with various activities and focuses on the learning outcomes and how to arrange specific activities to achieve those outcomes. Using Gagne's nine-step model is an excellent way to ensure an effective and systematic learning program as it gives structure to the lesson plans and a holistic view to the teaching. Choosing appropriate instructional activities and planning them in the right format and the right sequence is crucial to a successful lesson plan. A lesson plan is a plan

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showing the instructional activities of the teacher and the learner, their order and the kind of activity taking place in each step or stage.

Robert Gagne is considered to be one of the foremost contributors to the systematic approach to instructional design and his theory has provided a great number of valuable ideas for trainers and teachers. Gagne's model of instructional design is based on the information processing model of the mental events that occur when adults are presented with various stimuli and focuses on the learning outcomes and how to arrange specific instructional events to achieve those outcomes. Gagne's theories have been applied to the design of instruction in several domains, such as the military, flying, leadership, engineering and healthcare. Essential to Gagne's ideas of instruction are what he calls "conditions of learning": internal conditions deal with what the learner knows prior to the instruction, external conditions deal with the stimuli that are presented to the learner, e.g. instructions provided by the teacher.

Adeyemi (2018,) also investigated the effect of Gagne's hierarchical learning strategy and expository instructional methods on the motivated attitude of students to computer networking which is a topic in computer studies. Numerous studies have been conducted in the field of education on how teaching methods, instructor attitude and other factors affect students' motivation. According to research, students' motivation and academic achievement may be significantly impacted by the expertise and pedagogical methods of their instructors as well as the accessibility and utilization of university resources. The teacher's ability to create a mastery-oriented classroom environment in which students feel challenged and supported in their learning, can positively affect students' motivation, performance and achievement.

The data network developed as a result of the need to share or exchange electronic information across long distance, whether in private, public or business agencies. Computer network is a way of cutting down the cost of duplicating resources and reducing inaccuracies to the minimum as communication passes from one source to another. The computer network became prominent from the 1980's. A computer networking is a system that connects two or more computing devices for transmitting and sharing of information. A computer network is a digital telecommunications network which allows nodes to share resources, (Charles, 2020).

It was observed that learners demonstrate higher levels of engagement, motivation, and happiness when teachers use teaching methods that correspond to the students' preferred learning styles. Research on learning strategies has shown that students may adopt more than one learning strategy since different academic activities and their nature demand different processing strategies, which range from simple to more complex strategies.

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Computer networking is defined as when two or more computers are linked together (or connected) by communication channels and networking devices, they form a computer network. The communication channels can either be wire or wireless

TYPES OF NETWORKS

Ethernet: - is the most popular of all LAN technologies. Hence when you work in a bank, school, or cybercafé, you will likely encounter an Ethernet network. It was developed by Xerox Corporation in cooperation with DEC and Intel in 1976. It uses a bus or star topology and supports data transfer rate of 10 Mbps (megabits per second) to 10Gbps (Gega bits per second). On an Ethernet network, computers are connected coaxial cables twisted pair cables RJ-45 connector. The modern computers have an in built Ethernet port, into which RJ-45 connectors can be plugged in.

ARC Net: - This stand for Attached Resource Computer Network. Developed by Data Point Corporation in 1977. It is one of the oldest, the simplest, and the least expensive type of all LAN technologies. It uses token ring architecture; support data rate of 2.5 Mbps and connect up to 255 computer. It supports various types of cable such as coaxial, twisted pair and optic fiber,

TOKEN RING: - Is a type LAN formed by connecting computer in a ring forma. Message transfer is based on token passing. A toking is simply a bit pattern. Only one node can transmit at a time. The node that grabs the token as it circulates has the right to transmit. To transmit a message a node catches the token, place message with the address of the recipient, and then passes it on.

NETWORK TOPOLOGY

Network physical topology refers to the way in which computers and network devices are arranged and interconnected to form a network. The most common network topologies include Star, Bus, and ring.

STAR TOPOLOGY

In a star topology all devices are connected to a central connection point such as a hub or switch. The devices are connected to the central point using twisted pair cables. All information must pass through the central point; therefore, if the central point become faulty the network fails.

BUS TOPOLOGY

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In a bus topology, all devices are connected to a single cable called a backbone. The backbone serves as a shared communication medium. All devices transmit data through each computer until it gets to the recipient

RING TOPOLOGY

In a ring topology, each computer is connected to another computer, with the last one connected to the first, to form a closed loop (or ring). Data being transmitted passes through each computer until it gets to the recipient.

NETWORK DEVICES

Network devices are used to connect computers and computing devices to form a network, for the purpose of resource sharing. The most common network devices include hubs, modems, switches, routers, and network interface. According to Charles, (2020), the network components are:

Switches: Switches work as a controller which connects computers, printers, and other hardware devices to a network in a campus or a building. It allows devices on your network to communicate with each other, as well as with other networks. It helps you to share resources and reduce the costing of any organization.

Routers: Routers help you to connect with multiple networks. It enables you to share a single internet connection with multiple devices and saves money. This networking component acts as a dispatcher, which allows you to analyze data sent across a network. It automatically selects the best route for data to travel and send it on its way.

Servers: Servers are computers that hold shared programs, files, and the network operating system. Servers allow access to network resources to all the users of the network.

Clients: Clients are computer devices which access and uses the network as well as shares network resources. They are also users of the network, as they can send and receive requests from the server.

Transmission Media: Transmission media is a carrier used to interconnect computers in a network, such as coaxial cable, twisted-pair wire, and optical fiber cable. It is also known as links, channels, or lines.

Access points: Access points allow devices to connect to the wireless network without cables. A wireless network allows you to bring new devices and provides flexible support to mobile users. Shared Data: Shared data are data which is shared between the clients such as data files, printer access programs, and email.

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Network Interface Card: Network Interface card sends, receives data, and controls data flow between the computer and the network.

Local Operating System: A local OS which helps personal computers to access files, print to a local printer and uses one or more disk and CD drives which are located on the computer.

Network Operating System: The network operating system is a program which runs on computers and servers. It allows the computers to communicate via network.

Protocol: A protocol is the set of defined rules that allows two entities to communicate across the network. Some standard protocols used for this purpose are IP, TCP, UDP, FTP, etc.

Hub: Hub is a device that splits network connection into multiple computers. It acts a distribution center so whenever a computer requests any information from a computer or from the network it sends the request to the hub through a cable. The hub will receive the request and transmit it to the entire network.

LAN Cable: Local Area Network (LAN) cable is also called as Ethernet or data cable. It is used for connecting a device to the internet.

OSI: OSI stands for Open Systems Interconnection. It is a reference model which allows you to specify standards for communications.

Benefits of Networking

Although it costs to install a network, networking has immense benefits. Some of the benefits include the following:

Resource Sharing: Hardware resources like printers and scanners can be shared across a network instead of buying for each computer. Software resources such as programs and data can also be shared.

Ease of Communication: Message can be cheaply, instantly and reliably sent across a network by E-mail or instant messaging.

Ease Collaboration: A group of individuals working on a common project can share files, view other people's work, and exchange ideas more efficiently.

According to Sanjoy, (2024), Robert Gagné, the educational psychologist, came up with a plan called Gagné's Nine Events of Instruction. This plan helps make learning experiences

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better. It combines different learning ideas to help design instruction in digital settings, these are:

- i. Getting Attention: The first step is to grab attention to start learning In digital learning, use interactive stuff like games or animations. These things get learners focused and ready for new info.
- ii. Telling Learners the Goals: Next, make sure learners know what they need to learn, use videos or pop-ups to explain goals clearly. This helps learners know what to expect and keeps them motivated.
- iii. Recalling Past Knowledge: It is essential to connect new facts to what learners already know. Digital tools like quizzes help remind learners of old stuff they learned. This makes it easier for them to understand new info.
- iv. Showing the Info: Using images along with words helps people learn better. Digital learning can use videos and simulations to explain things more clearly. Different types of media work for different learners.
- v. Giving Support: Learners need help until they can do things on their own. Digital programs can have tutors or hints to guide learners through tasks. Personalized help keeps learners on track.
- vi. Practicing Skills: Practice makes perfect when it comes to learning. Online platforms offer exercises that let learners try out what they've learned. Feedback helps them improve as they practice.
- vii. Getting Feedback: Feedback helps people improve by showing them what's right or wrong. Online quizzes and exercises with instant results give feedback right away. This lets learners see where they need to work harder.
- viii. Checking Progress: Assessing progress ensures goals are met. Online tests and tasks track how well learners are doing. Data shows what areas need more work. Remembering and Using Knowledge: Using different methods helps keep knowledge fresh in the mind.
- ix. Practicing skills in real-life scenarios makes knowledge stick better. Digital tools simulate real situations where learners can apply what they've learned.

In designing a session like this, several factors need to be considered, including the nature of objectives, setting, time, available resources, institutional constraints, content and number of learners, their characteristics and their preferences. The most effective way to achieve objectives is to get the learners to perform and practice the activity after preparing them with some lessons or demonstrations. The performance most frequently required of students is to remember, while our intent is most often to help them understand, and by putting more structure into the objectives of the lesson plans we will be able to achieve these objectives.

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As Gagne himself says, "organization is the hallmark of effective instructional materials". Gagne's Educational Implications. To Gagne, learning is the learner's activity. The teacher cannot substitute his activity for that of the student. However, the teacher can provide necessary conditions in which the student can learn more

Gagne's learning hierarchy is useful in teaching Applications in teaching Gagne are learning hierarchy helps the teacher identify suitable learning types for the learners.

- i. It helps the teacher select appropriate teaching technique
- ii. It helps the teacher select suitable content or unit for teaching for teaching
- iii. It helps the teacher decide what lower behaviors or subordinate skills should be taught before teaching higher learning types.
- iv. It helps the teacher to break a complex task into component skills and teach those skills only that the students are lacking.
- v. Textbooks can be produced on the basis of the task analysis of learning objectives.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to:

- i. Determine the effect of Gagnes nine levels of learning strategies on secondary school students' motivation in computer networking in Zamfara State
- ii. find out whether Gagne learning strategy has effect on gender's motivation.

Research questions

The following are the questions raised to guide the study:

- i. What is the mean difference in the motivation between students that were taught Computer networking with Gagne hierarchical learning and those taught with discussion method?
- ii. What is the mean difference in the motivation between male and female students that were taught computer networking using Gagne hierarchical learning?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the motivation between students taught Computer Networking using Gagne hierarchical learning and those taught using discussion method.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the motivation between male and female students taught Computer Networking using Gagne hierarchical learning.

Methodology

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A mixed research design (comprising of quasi-experimental and survey research design) was adopted for this study. The research design involved the implementation of pre-test and post-test measures to evaluate the effect of Gagne nine levels of learning strategy and discussion method on the academic performance of SS2 students on computer networking. The study used intact classes, specifically focusing on SS2 students, where two groups were formed, an experimental group that received instruction using Gagne nine levels of learning strategy and control group that received instruction using discussion method. The use of a quasi-experimental design allows for a comparison between the two groups while considering the existing group composition.

The population of the study consisted of SS2 students offering data processing in all secondary schools in Gusau. A purposive sampling technique was used to select the sample for the study. From the selected schools, two intact classes were included in the study. The sample size was determined based on the number of students in each intact class. This gave a number of 98 sample size.

The research instrument used to collect data for the study was the Computer networking motivation questionnaire (CNMQ) and Computer Networking Performance Test (CNPT).

Procedure for Data Collection

The data collection process involved conducting a pre-test to assess the academic performance in computer networking for both the experimental and control groups. The experimental group received instruction using Gagne nine's levels of learning strategy, while the control group received instruction with discussion method. Posttest was administered after the intervention to measure the impact of the instructional methods. The data collection process was carried out for six weeks to ensure consistency and minimize external factors that could influence the students' performance.

Presentation of Results

The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation,

Research question 1

What is the mean difference in the motivation between student taught Computer networking with Gagne hierarchical learning and those taught with lecture method?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation showing motivation of students in the learning of computer networking

S/N	Student group	No	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)	Decision
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1	Experimental	47	42.23	5.031	More effective
2	Control	51	29.47	6.821	Effective

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The data on students' performance in Table I revealed that students taught Computer networking using Gagne hierarchical learning motivation had a mean motivation score of 42.23 with a standard deviation of 5.03 while the mean motivation score of students taught with the conventional lecture method is 29.47 with a standard deviation of 6.82. Students taught Computer networking using Gagne hierarchical learning method were motivated higher than students taught using the conventional lecture method. The difference of 12.76 in favor of experimental group.

Research question 2

What is the mean difference in motivation between male and female students taught Computer networking using Gagne hierarchical motivate learning?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation showing motivation of students based on Gender

S/N	Gender	No	Mean	Standard deviation	Decision
1	Male	27	41.66	4.835	Good Performance
2	Female	20	43.00	5.311	Better Performance

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Data in Table 2 revealed a mean motivation score of 41.66 with a standard deviation of 4.83 for male students, while the female students had a mean motivation learning score of 43.00 with a standard deviation of 5.31. The students learning motivation in Computer networking studies of female students is higher than that of the male student by 1.44.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the motivation between students taught Computer Networking with Gagne hierarchical learning and those taught with lecture method.

Table 3: t-test showing students' motivation on learning of computer networking

S/N	Std group	No	Mean	SD	Df	tcal	Decision
1	Experimental	48	42.23	5.031			

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96 10.46 Rejected

2	Control	50	29.17	6.821			
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Source; Fieldwork, 2025

From Table 3, the result revealed that the t-cal was 10.46 and a p-value of 0.00 was recorded at df = 96. Since the p-value of p=0.00 is less than 0.05, it implies that there is a significant difference in the learning motivation between students that was taught Computer networking with Gagne hierarchical learning and those taught with the lecture method. Thus, the null hypothesis that says there is no significant difference is rejected:

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between male and female students taught Computer networking using Gagne hierarchical levels of learning.

Table 4: t-test showing male and female students' motivation in Computer networking using Gagne's hierarchical learning.

S/N	Group	No	Mean	SD	Df	t.cal	Decision
1	Male	48	41.66	4.8835	96	-0.89	Accepted
2	Female	50	43.00	5.311			

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

From Table 4 the result revealed that t-cal was -0.89 and a p-value of 0.957 was recorded at df=96. Since the p-value of p=0.957 is greater than 0.05, it implies that there is no significant difference between male and female students taught Computer Networking using Gagne hierarchical motivate learning. Thus, the null hypothesis that says there is no significant difference was accepted.

Discussion of Findings

As seen from the result of testing hypothesis one shows that there is a significant difference in the motivation mean scores of students exposed to Gagne hierarchical learning and those taught using discussion method. The significant difference found between the two groups is likely to be due to the use of the Gagne hierarchical learning strategy in the experimental group. The result confirms the earlier finding of Sabiru (2013) and Ugwu (2015) who recommended that students should be provided with the appropriate method of instruction in science such as the Gagne hierarchical learning strategy in order to make abstract concepts better understood.

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Similarly, Tang, Tsai and Huang (2020), affirmed that these motivational learning strategies help in diagnosing student learning difficulties and providing the teacher with ways of improving learning effectiveness. On the issue of gender in relation to the motivational learning achievement academic achievement when Gagne hierarchical learning and lecture method were employed, the results in table 4 shows that Gagne hierarchical learning enhances strong motivation in the learning behavior of both male and female students in Computer networking in Zamfara State's Senior Secondary schools.

Conclusion

The results indicated that the performance of students taught Computer Networking concept using Gagne hierarchical learning strategy was significantly better, students' gender had no significant effect on their learning motivation in Computer networking as compared to Gagne's hierarchical learning strategy. Since the experimental group performed significantly better, it implies that using Gagne hierarchical learning in teaching students improves their motivation.

Recommendations

- i. In-service training for science teachers in form of seminars, workshops, and conferences should focus more on how to use various instructional strategies especially Gagne hierarchical learning strategy for the teaching of Computer studies and the learning of computer networking in particular.
- ii. This Gagne's method of instruction should be employed in other topics of computer studies and in other science subjects.

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